

The Jovanović adsorption isotherm in water contaminant research: Unmasking spurious versions and spotlighting the real thing

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Abstract

This study evaluates the capability of the Jovanović isotherm in correlating water contaminant adsorption data. Both incorrect and correct formulations of the isotherm are examined. Two flawed versions lead to negative adsorption equilibrium constants when fitting experimental data. These results are nonsensical and contradict the conventional definition of equilibrium constants. In contrast, the genuine Jovanović isotherm proves to be a valuable model for describing favorable or type I isotherm data. It serves as a practical alternative to the widely used Langmuir isotherm. Additionally, this research evaluates a rarely used version of the Jovanović isotherm specifically developed for multilayer adsorption. The findings reveal that a modified adaptation of the multilayer adsorption isotherm is superior to the original formulation, enabling an accurate representation of sigmoid or type II isotherm data. Moreover,

this work demonstrates that by assuming Jovanović local behavior, global isotherms capable of representing adsorption on heterogeneous adsorbents can be obtained.

Keywords: Energy distribution; Global isotherm; Jovanovich isotherm; Misuse; Misconception; Thermodynamic parameter

1. Introduction

The field of water contaminant adsorption has a long tradition of interactions between experimental and modeling approaches. The major phenomena of interest are those that pertain to adsorption equilibria and kinetics. In the subfield of adsorption equilibria, experimental data are commonly interpreted using an assortment of isotherm models originally developed for gas adsorption on solid surfaces. Of these models, the more than century-old Langmuir isotherm (Langmuir, 1916) is undoubtedly the most prominent one. The immense popularity of the Langmuir isotherm is in large part due to its simple mathematical form, which allows the use of linear regression to estimate its two fitting parameters. Some other popular models belonging to this category are those of Freundlich (1907), Elovich (Dusart et al., 1991), Temkin (1979), and Dubinin and Radushkevich (Dubinin, 1975). Modern takes on these simple isotherm models are available in the literature (Chu, 2021a; Debord et al., 2022, 2023; Puccia and Avena, 2021; Swenson and Stadie, 2019).

Although the Jovanović isotherm is also a simple analytical expression with two fitting parameters, it has not been as widely used as some of the aforementioned models. Developed in the late 1960s for gas phase adsorption, the Jovanović isotherm is more than 50 years old (Jovanović, 1969a). Its theoretical foundation is based on a more refined conception of Langmuir's theory of adsorption. It should be emphasized that there are two versions of the Jovanović isotherm: one for monolayer adsorption and one for multilayer adsorption. Because the latter version has practically faded into oblivion, the term "Jovanović isotherm" is generally understood to denote the former version.

A notable application of the Jovanović isotherm can be found in the area of gas adsorption on heterogeneous adsorbents. It has been used as the local isotherm in conjunction with various energy distribution functions to derive global isotherms (Hassan et al., 1992; Hines et al., 1990; Jaroniec and Piotrowska, 1986; Misra, 1973; Sircar, 1984). In liquid phase adsorption studies, the Jovanović isotherm was probably first used by Huang and Horváth (1987a, 1987b) to describe the adsorption of biomolecules on liquid chromatographic sorbents.

The use of the Jovanović isotherm in water contaminant research is a more recent development. It was first applied to the adsorption of dyes on activated carbons in the 2010s

(Hadi et al., 2010, 2012; McKay et al., 2014). Since then, it has been increasingly used to interpret the adsorption data of a multitude of water contaminants, including micropollutants or contaminants of emerging concern (Balasubramani et al., 2020; Bandura et al., 2021; Priyan et al., 2021). However, it is somewhat difficult to gauge the capabilities and limitations of the Jovanović isotherm from previously published modeling results. The reason for this murky situation is that flawed versions of the Jovanović isotherm have pervaded the literature on water contaminant adsorption. As such, most of the published modeling results pertaining to the Jovanović isotherm have been largely meaningless or misleading.

The primary aim of the present paper is to highlight the incorrect forms of the Jovanović isotherm and evaluate the genuine Jovanović isotherm's efficacy as a modeling tool in water contaminant adsorption studies. To achieve this goal, we have set out to (1) compare the Jovanović isotherm for monolayer adsorption, the Langmuir isotherm, and two Jovanović variants by using published isotherm data; (2) scrutinize two spurious forms of the Jovanović isotherm for monolayer adsorption; (3) evaluate the obscure Jovanović isotherm for multilayer adsorption; and (4) derive global isotherms for heterogeneous adsorbents by assuming Jovanović local behavior.

2. Theoretical background

Jovanović's theory of gas adsorption rested upon Langmuir's theory of monolayer adsorption on a homogeneous surface without lateral interactions (Jovanović, 1969a). The celebrated Langmuir model for gas adsorption is given by Eq. (1), where θ is the surface coverage at equilibrium, b_L is the adsorption equilibrium constant, and p is the gas pressure at equilibrium.

$$\theta = \frac{b_L p}{1 + b_L p} \quad (1)$$

By considering additional collisions (apparently not taken into account by the Langmuir model) between adsorbing and desorbing molecules, which are responsible for the re-adsorption of just desorbed molecules, Jovanović derived Eq. (2), where b is the adsorption equilibrium constant for monolayer adsorption (Jovanović, 1969a). Jovanović extended his theory of gas adsorption to cover the case of multilayer adsorption, deriving Eq. (3), where the two equilibrium constants b and k describe adsorption in the first and in the second and higher layers, respectively. In a related paper (Jovanović, 1969b), Jovanović demonstrated the practical utility of his equations in correlating gas adsorption data. Note that Eq. (2) is

analogous to the cumulative exponential distribution function used in probability theory and statistics (Devore, 2016).

$$\theta = 1 - \exp(-bp) \quad (2)$$

$$\theta = [1 - \exp(-bp)] \exp(kp) \quad (3)$$

While Eq. (2) was also derived by several researchers using different methods (Cerofolini, 1978; Jaroniec, 1976a; Kudzinski and Wojciechowski, 1977; Misra, 1980), Jovanović's derivation was contested by Hazlett et al. (1979), who argued that Jovanović's depiction of the re-adsorption process was incomplete. Jovanović suggested that the effect of collision is limited to (i) just desorbed molecules and impinging bulk phase molecules. Hazlett et al. (1979) showed that, in reality, it also applies to (ii) desorbed molecules which are fully detached from the surface and bulk phase molecules. Interestingly, taking into account both (i) and (ii) types of collision leads to an equation of the Langmuir form instead of Eq. (2). Despite the controversial nature of Jovanović's adsorption theory, Eq. (2) has been widely used to interpret gas adsorption data.

As previously mentioned, there have been several alternative methods used to derive Eq. (2). One interesting approach is evident in the research conducted by Misra (1980), wherein a semi-empirical technique was used to investigate the relationship between the Jovanović and Langmuir isotherms. The differential form of these two models, presented in Eq. (4), differs only in the value of the exponent σ , which corresponds to 1 and 2 for the Jovanović and Langmuir models, respectively. The parameter λ in Eq. (4) denotes the adsorption equilibrium constant in the Langmuir model [b_L in Eq. (1)] or the Jovanović model [b in Eq. (2)]. Furthermore, Eq. (2) was obtained by Schaetzel et al. (2017, 2021) using a generalized Henry's law that does not depend on molecular collision assumptions. Nevertheless, there are some similarities in the methods used by Schaetzel et al. (2017, 2021) and Misra (1980).

$$\frac{d\theta}{dp} = \lambda(1-\theta)^\sigma \quad (4)$$

In order to describe adsorption in the liquid phase, Huang and Horváth (1987a) transformed Eq. (2) into Eq. (5). Eq. (3) can be converted into Eq. (6) in a similar manner. In this conversion, the gas pressure is substituted with the solute concentration in the liquid phase. This conversion remains applicable as long as the solute concentration is sufficiently low and the solute exhibits strong adsorption behavior. In these two equations, q is the adsorbed phase concentration at equilibrium, q_J is the saturation capacity, and c is the liquid phase

concentration at equilibrium. In this work, Eq. (5) is called the Jovanović-I isotherm, while Eq. (6) is referred to as the Jovanović-II isotherm.

$$\theta = \frac{q}{q_J} = [1 - \exp(-bc)] \quad (5)$$

$$\theta = \frac{q}{q_J} = [1 - \exp(-bc)] \exp(kc) \quad (6)$$

3. Model fitting and evaluation

In this study, various isotherm models were fitted to multiple datasets from previous publications using a nonlinear regression technique. To extract the data points from the original sources, Engauge Digitizer (<https://markummittchell.github.io/engauge-digitizer/>) was used. The performance of the isotherm models was evaluated using two indicators: the average percent error (APE) and the Akaike weight (AW). The APE indicator, defined in Eq. (7), incorporates the experimental value of q (q_{exp}), the calculated value of q from an isotherm model (q_{cal}), and the total number of data points (z).

$$APE = \frac{100}{z} \sum_{i=1}^z \frac{|q_{exp,i} - q_{cal,i}|}{q_{exp,i}} \quad (7)$$

The AW metric, presented in Eqs. (8)–(11), defines several key components. The sum of squared residuals (SSR) quantifies the discrepancy between the model and the observed data. The corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) incorporates a penalty for the number of fitting parameters (h). AIC_i represents the AIC value for the i -th model, while AIC_s corresponds to the AIC value for the model with the lowest score. Additionally, w denotes the number of competing models. The AW metric offers an estimate of the probability that the model with the lowest AIC value is the correct choice. It facilitates a comparative assessment of fit quality among models that differ in the number of fitting parameters.

$$SSR = \sum_{i=1}^z (q_{exp,i} - q_{cal,i})^2 \quad (8)$$

$$AIC = z \ln \left(\frac{SSR}{z} \right) + \frac{2z(h+1)}{z-h-2} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta_i = AIC_i - AIC_s \quad (10)$$

$$AW = 100 \frac{\exp(-0.5\Delta_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^w \exp(-0.5\Delta_j)} \quad (11)$$

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Comparing Langmuir and Jovanović-I

As noted above, the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms are closely related, underscoring the importance of comparing their characteristics. In the context of liquid phase adsorption, the Langmuir model, as described by Eq. (1), can be expressed in a modified form, denoted as Eq. (12), wherein q_s represents the saturation capacity. Fig. 1A illustrates both isotherms in a dimensionless manner, displaying curves of θ versus $b_L c$ or bc . As $b_L c$ or bc increases, discrepancies arise between the θ values of the two isotherms, with the Jovanović-I isotherm reaching saturation more quickly than the Langmuir isotherm. Consequently, fitting both isotherms to a specific dataset would yield distinct behaviors, an aspect that will be further examined later. Fig. 1B shows that at low concentrations, both isotherms converge to the same linear correlation, with the slope of the line representing the Henry's law constant.

$$\theta = \frac{q}{q_s} = \frac{b_L c}{1 + b_L c} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 1. Comparing the dimensionless Langmuir and dimensionless Jovanović-I isotherms (A) and the same isotherms in the low concentration region (B).

To validate the observation presented in Fig. 1A, indicating that the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms produce different fits for a given dataset, both isotherms were applied to previously published experimental data. Fig. 2A displays the first dataset, obtained from the research conducted by Wongcharee et al. (2019), which describes the adsorption of methylene blue on a composite adsorbent at 25 °C. The experimental isotherm exhibits a gradual increase in q with increasing c , eventually reaching a distinct plateau at high c values.

Fig. 2A compares the fits obtained from the Langmuir and Jovanović-I models, with the latter exhibiting superior performance. This observation is further supported by the fit

statistics presented in Table 1. Both the APE and AW indicators confirm that the Jovanović-I isotherm provides a more accurate representation compared to the Langmuir isotherm. However, the conclusion drawn from Fig. 2A is not universally applicable. Additional examples provided in the Supplementary Data accompanying this publication demonstrate situations where the Langmuir isotherm outperforms the Jovanović-I isotherm in fitting data characterized by a distinct plateau.

Fig. 2. Fitting methylene blue adsorption data (Wongcharee et al., 2019) (A) and tetracycline adsorption data (Shen et al., 2022) (B) with the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms.

Table 1 Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the fits of the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms to methylene blue adsorption data (Wongcharee et al., 2019).^a

Isotherm	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value	Statistical metric	Value
Langmuir	(12)	q_s	101.8 (3.2)	APE	9.7	AW	0.0
		b_L	0.108 (0.01)				
Jovanović-I	(5)	q_I	86.03 (0.42)	APE	2.0	AW	100.0
		b	0.099 (0.001)				

^a q_s and q_I are in mg g^{-1} ; b_L and b are in L mg^{-1} ; APE and AW are in %.

The Langmuir and Jovanović-I models were also applied to another dataset obtained from the research conducted by Shen et al. (2022). In Fig. 2B, the experimental isotherm selected for analysis illustrates the adsorption behavior of tetracycline on a modified bentonite adsorbent known as CMS-MB in the original study. The overall shape of the tetracycline isotherm in Fig. 2B shows similarities to that of the methylene blue isotherm in Fig. 2A. However, in this particular case, the high concentration region does not exhibit a distinct plateau; instead, there is a gradual increase in q at high c values.

Fig. 2B reveals that the Langmuir model provides a more accurate representation of the experimental isotherm compared to the Jovanović-I model. This observation is strengthened

by the APE values presented in Table 2, indicating that the Langmuir isotherm fit yields a smaller error in comparison to the Jovanović-I isotherm fit. However, the conclusion drawn from Fig. 2B is not definitive. Additional examples provided in the Supplementary Data reveal that both models exhibit remarkably similar performance when representing data that lacks a distinct plateau.

Table 2 Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the fits of the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms to tetracycline adsorption data (Shen et al., 2022).^a

Isotherm	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value	Statistical metric	Value
Langmuir	(12)	q_s	158.6 (3.4)	APE	5.6	AW	99.9
		b_L	0.032 (0.002)				
Jovanović-I	(5)	q_J	134.8 (3.7)	APE	8.4	AW	0.1
		b	0.029 (0.002)				

^a q_s and q_J are in mg g^{-1} ; b_L and b are in L mg^{-1} ; APE and AW are in %.

The two cases analyzed above, along with the examples provided in the Supplementary Data, clearly illustrate that the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms exhibit distinct characteristics when applied to specific datasets, especially those featuring a distinct plateau. Moreover, it is noteworthy that the q_s value obtained from the Langmuir isotherm tends to be larger compared to the q_J value derived from the Jovanović-I isotherm, as indicated in Tables 1 and 2. However, the equilibrium constants b_L and b show relatively similar values.

As an aside, this study delves into the topic of thermodynamic calculations using the parameters of the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms. It is worth noting that the existing literature on this subject is plagued with numerous flawed calculations, as highlighted by Salvestrini et al. (2014, 2022). Within the field of adsorption studies, Eqs. (13)–(15) are commonly used to determine the thermodynamic adsorption parameters, namely ΔG° , ΔH° , and ΔS° (Salvestrini et al., 2022; Tran et al., 2023). These parameters correspond to the standard Gibbs energy, standard enthalpy, and standard entropy of adsorption, respectively. In these equations, K° represents the thermodynamic adsorption equilibrium constant (dimensionless), R denotes the universal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature.

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln(K^\circ) \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (14)$$

$$K^\circ = \exp\left(\frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{R} \frac{1}{T}\right) \quad (15)$$

In general, adsorption experiments are carried out at various temperatures, ideally with a minimum of four temperature points. For each temperature, an equilibrium constant is determined and plotted against T to calculate ΔH° and ΔS° using Eq. (15). However, this equation assumes that both ΔH° and ΔS° remain relatively constant across the temperature range. This assumption is reasonable when the temperature variations are smaller than 50 K (Atkins et al., 2022), as commonly observed in most adsorption studies.

In cases where ΔH° and ΔS° exhibit temperature dependence, modified versions of Eq. (15) are required, as noted by Salvestrini and Bollinger (2022). For example, the influence of temperature on ΔH° and ΔS° can be taken into account by considering Eqs. (16) and (17), respectively. In these equations, T_0 represents a reference temperature (e.g., 298 K) and ΔC_p° , assumed to be independent of temperature, represents the difference in heat capacities between the adsorbate-adsorbent complex and the unbound adsorbate and unoccupied binding sites. Additionally, the subscript T indicates the temperature-dependent nature of the respective parameter.

$$\Delta H^\circ_T = \Delta H^\circ_{T_0} + \Delta C_p^\circ (T - T_0) \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta S^\circ_T = \Delta S^\circ_{T_0} + \Delta C_p^\circ \ln\left(\frac{T}{T_0}\right) \quad (17)$$

Substituting Eqs. (16) and (17) into Eq. (15) results in the three-parameter model described in Eq. (18). This model can be fitted to a plot of K° versus T to obtain estimates for ΔC_p° , $\Delta H^\circ_{T_0}$, and $\Delta S^\circ_{T_0}$. It is important to note that obtaining reliable estimates for all three thermodynamic parameters would require adsorption equilibrium data from at least six different temperatures. When ΔC_p° is influenced by temperature, the relationship between K° and T becomes more complex. For instance, by assuming a Taylor's series expansion in T for ΔC_p° , a six-parameter equation can be derived (Clarke and Glew, 1966).

$$K^\circ = \exp\left[\frac{\Delta S^\circ_{T_0} + \Delta C_p^\circ \ln(T/T_0)}{R}\right] \exp\left[-\frac{\Delta H^\circ_{T_0} + \Delta C_p^\circ (T - T_0)}{RT}\right] \quad (18)$$

The accurate determination of thermodynamic parameters hinges on selecting an appropriate equilibrium constant, which in turn is influenced by the choice of the adsorption isotherm used to model the experimental data. When using the Langmuir isotherm, the adsorption equilibrium constant is represented by the Langmuir parameter b_L . However, the determination of the equilibrium constant is not as straightforward when using the Jovanović-I isotherm. The theoretical foundation of the Jovanović-I model is disputed, as mentioned in

Section 2. As a result, there exists some uncertainty regarding the interpretation of its parameter b , which is defined as the equilibrium constant for monolayer adsorption.

An alternative option is to use the partitioning equilibrium constant. According to Eq. (19), the partitioning equilibrium constant, denoted as K_0 , is defined as the first derivative of θ with respect to c at $c = 0$ (Salvestrini et al., 2014). Eq. (19) is applicable only when there is an abundance of unoccupied adsorption sites at low liquid phase concentrations ($c \rightarrow 0$). This condition leads to a linear adsorption isotherm, effectively simulating a partitioning process.

$$K_0 = \left(\frac{d\theta}{dc} \right)_{c=0} \quad (19)$$

By using Eqs. (5) and (19), the partitioning equilibrium constant (K_0) for the Jovanović-I isotherm, specifically denoted as $K_{0,J}$, can be derived as shown in Eq. (20). Interestingly, a similar result is observed for the Langmuir isotherm, where the partitioning equilibrium constant is represented as $K_{0,L} = b_L$. Consequently, it can be concluded that both the Jovanović-I isotherm and the Langmuir isotherm describe the same equilibrium state in dilute solutions.

$$K_{0,J} = b \quad (20)$$

By using Eqs. (13)–(15) in conjunction with Eq. (20), it is possible to determine the thermodynamic adsorption parameters using the Jovanović-I isotherm. To demonstrate this, we will recalculate the thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of methylene blue on a composite adsorbent, as originally presented by Wongcharee et al. (2019). The authors observed better fitting results for the Jovanović-I isotherm in comparison to the Langmuir model, although an incorrect form of the Jovanović-I isotherm was used in their study. Nevertheless, they used the equilibrium constant from the Langmuir model to calculate the thermodynamic parameters. Table 3 provides a comparison between the thermodynamic parameters calculated by Wongcharee et al. (2019) (using the Langmuir model) and those obtained by us using the genuine Jovanović-I isotherm. As expected, based on our earlier discussion, the equilibrium constants from both isotherm models are quite similar, resulting in comparable thermodynamic parameters.

Table 3 Comparison of thermodynamic parameters obtained by using the Langmuir model in the original study (Wongcharee et al., 2019) and the Jovanović-I model in the present study.^a

Temp. (K)	b_L°		b°		ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔS° (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	
	Original study	Present study	Original study	Present study	Original study	Present study	Original study	Present study	Original study	Present study
298	34.7×10^3	31.7×10^3	-25.90	-25.68						
308	81.8×10^3	67.1×10^3	-28.97	-28.46	55.55	51.22	0.27	0.26		
318	154.6×10^3	122.0×10^3	-31.59	-30.97						

^a Solute standard state, $c^\circ = 1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.

4.2. Comparing Langmuir, Jovanović-I, and Jovanović-I variants

In the previous section, we analyzed the experimental isotherms of methylene blue and tetracycline, which exhibited typical hyperbolic curves that posed no significant challenges for the Langmuir and Jovanović-I models. In this section, we will conduct a comprehensive evaluation of these models using more challenging experimental data. The comparative analysis will encompass two variants of the Jovanović-I isotherm.

The first variant is represented by Eq. (21), proposed by Quiñones and Guiochon (1996) to describe gas adsorption equilibria on heterogeneous surfaces. This variant incorporates three adjustable parameters: q_J , b , and n , where n denotes the heterogeneity parameter. In this study, we refer to Eq. (21) as the power-law Jovanović-I equation. When n is equal to 1, Eq. (21) simplifies to the original Jovanović-I equation. As the liquid phase concentration c approaches higher values, the ratio of q to q_J tends toward unity. However, for lower c values, Eq. (21) behaves like the Freundlich isotherm, deviating from the Henry law.

$$q = q_J \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[-(bc)^n \right] \right\} \quad (21)$$

It is worth noting that Eq. (21) is analogous to the cumulative Weibull distribution function used in probability theory and statistics (Devore, 2016). As a result, Eq. (21) is capable of predicting hyperbolic curves when $n \leq 1$ and sigmoid curves when $n > 1$ (Chu, 2021b). The power-law Jovanović-I equation has also been proposed by other researchers. For example, the Brouers–Sotolongo isotherm, as acknowledged by Brouers and Marquez-Montesino (2016), is equivalent to Eq. (21). The Brouers–Sotolongo isotherm is based on the Burr type XII distribution, which can be simplified to the Weibull distribution under certain circumstances. Additionally, the isotherm model proposed by Zhou et al. (2001) is indistinguishable from Eq. (21). This equivalence is not surprising, considering that the Weibull distribution was used in the development of their model.

Eq. (22) describes the second variant of the Jovanović-I model used in this study. Initially proposed by Medve et al. (1997) to study the adsorption of enzymes on cellulose, Eq. (22) assumes the presence of two distinct and independent adsorption sites on the surface of a heterogeneous adsorbent. In Eq. (22), q_{JA} and q_{JB} represent the saturation capacities for type A and type B sites, respectively, while b_A and b_B denote the equilibrium constants for type A and type B sites, respectively. As such, this variant encompasses four numerical parameters. Essentially, Eq. (22) resembles the well-known two-site Langmuir model (Graham, 1953) and can be viewed as a direct extension of the original Jovanović-I isotherm. Therefore, its behavior at low and high concentrations is similar to that of the Jovanović-I isotherm. In this study, we refer to Eq. (22) as the two-site Jovanović-I equation.

$$q = q_{JA} [1 - \exp(-b_A c)] + q_{JB} [1 - \exp(-b_B c)] \quad (22)$$

Fig. 3. Fitting acid red 18 adsorption data (Vargas et al., 2012) with the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms (A) and with the power-law Jovanović-I and two-site Jovanović-I isotherms (B).

The four isotherm models (Langmuir, Jovanović-I, power-law Jovanović-I, and two-site Jovanović-I) were applied to two atypical datasets. The first dataset, obtained from the study conducted by Vargas et al. (2012), concerns the adsorption of acid red 18 on activated carbon. Fig. 3 illustrates the isotherm of the dye, which exhibits a hyperbolic curve shape characterized by a steep ascending part and a distinct plateau in the high concentration region. This particular curve shape, often referred to as irreversible or rectangular, is not commonly observed in studies focusing on water contaminant adsorption.

Table 4 Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the fits of the Langmuir, Jovanović-I, power-law Jovanović-I, and two-site Jovanović-I isotherms to acid red 18 adsorption data (Vargas et al., 2012).^a

Isotherm	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value	Statistical metric	Value
Langmuir	(12)	q_s	606.94 (16.27)	APE	6.9	AW	5.1
		b_L	1.42 (0.22)				
Jovanović-I	(5)	q_J	591.91 (19.73)	APE	8.1	AW	0.5
		b	1.07 (0.16)				
Power-law Jovanović-I	(21)	q_J	615.5 (23.7)	APE	13.6	AW	0.0
		b	0.477 (0.2)				
Two-site Jovanović-I	(22)	n	0.449 (0.1)	APE	1.4	AW	94.4
		q_{JA}	481.8 (18.14)				
		b_A	1.5 (0.12)				
		q_{JB}	162.3 (18.91)				
		b_B	0.013 (0.004)				

^a q_s , q_J , q_{JA} , and q_{JB} are in mg g^{-1} ; b_L , b , b_A , and b_B are in L mg^{-1} ; n is dimensionless; APE and AW are in %.

Fig. 3 showcases the fits of the four isotherm models to the dye adsorption data, while Table 4 presents the corresponding parameter estimates and fit statistics. The APE scores provided in Table 4 indicate that the two-site Jovanović-I equation offers the most accurate fit. The four models are ranked in ascending order of correlation accuracy as follows: power-law Jovanović-I < Jovanović-I < Langmuir < two-site Jovanović-I. The AW metric strongly supports the use of the two-site Jovanović-I model although it has four fitting parameters. Generally, for typical hyperbolic curves like the methylene blue isotherm displayed in Fig. 2A, using isotherm models with more than two free parameters is unnecessary. When applied to the methylene blue isotherm, the power-law Jovanović-I and two-site Jovanović-I equations exhibit highly accurate fits, with parameter estimates of $n = 1$ and $b_{JB} = 0$. These estimates indicate that the two models can be simplified to the original two-parameter Jovanović-I isotherm without sacrificing accuracy.

The second dataset, obtained from the work of Ma et al. (2022), describes the adsorption of tetracycline using a biochar adsorbent called MNSBC. As shown in Fig. 4, the tetracycline isotherm exhibits a hyperbolic curve without a distinct plateau, characterized by a gradual increase in q at higher concentrations. Fig. 4A reveals considerable discrepancies between the experimental data and the fits generated by the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms. In contrast, Fig. 4B demonstrates that both the power-law Jovanović-I and two-site Jovanović-I equations exhibit significant capability in accurately representing the experimental isotherm.

Fig. 4. Fitting tetracycline adsorption data (Ma et al., 2022) with the Langmuir and Jovanović-I isotherms (A) and with the power-law Jovanović-I and two-site Jovanović-I isotherms (B).

The APE values presented in Table 5 indicate that the two-site Jovanović-I equation exhibits a slight superiority over the power-law Jovanović-I equation. However, the small advantage of the two-site Jovanović-I equation fit is not significant enough to warrant the use of four fitting parameters, as indicated by the AW metric. Therefore, the AW metric favors the power-law Jovanović-I equation, which uses three fitting parameters. From a statistical perspective, the power-law Jovanović-I equation appears to be the most appropriate model for describing the tetracycline isotherm. However, the standard errors for two out of the three parameters in the power-law Jovanović-I equation, specifically q_I and b , are comparable to or significantly larger than their respective best-fit values (as shown in Table 5). This suggests that the available data may not be sufficient to accurately determine all three parameters. Given that the tetracycline isotherm is defined by only seven data points, the acquisition of additional data could potentially reduce the standard errors for q_I and b , resulting in a more precise estimation of the parameters.

Table 5 Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the fits of the Langmuir, Jovanović-I, power-law Jovanović-I, and two-site Jovanović-I isotherms to tetracycline adsorption data (Ma et al., 2022).^a

Isotherm	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value	Statistical metric	Value
Langmuir	(12)	q_s	190.7 (10.9)	APE	7.8	AW	24.8
		b_L	0.078 (0.02)				
Jovanović-I	(5)	q_I	165.6 (10.0)	APE	11.9	AW	1.0
		b	0.065 (0.02)				
Power-law Jovanović-I	(21)	q_I	413.5 (325.1)	APE	2.5	AW	74.2
		b	0.002 (0.006)				

Two-site Jovanović-I	(22)	n	0.364 (0.07)	APE	1.0	AW	0.0
		q_{JA}	84.95 (5.8)				
		b_A	0.239 (0.034)				
		q_{JB}	136.8 (9.4)				
		b_B	0.01 (0.002)				

^a q_s , q_J , q_{JA} , and q_{JB} are in mg g^{-1} ; b_L , b , b_A , and b_B are in L mg^{-1} ; n is dimensionless; APE and AW are in %.

It should be pointed out that obtaining a satisfactory fit for the tetracycline isotherm, which lacks a visible plateau, does not necessarily require the use of isotherm models that involve more than two adjustable parameters, such as the power-law Jovanović-I equation. Although fitting the tetracycline isotherm may pose challenges when using the two-parameter Jovanović-I and Langmuir equations, other two-parameter models like the Freundlich equation can accurately describe adsorption isotherms of this nature.

In summary, the Jovanović-I isotherm, similar to the Langmuir isotherm, is effective in describing typical hyperbolic isotherms that feature a distinct plateau, as illustrated in Fig. 2A. However, isotherms that lack a clearly defined plateau and instead exhibit a gradual increase in q at higher concentrations, as shown in Fig. 4, can pose a challenge for the Jovanović-I isotherm due to its inherent design for modeling adsorption that reaches saturation. Additionally, the Jovanović-I isotherm is not suitable for fitting the rectangular isotherm depicted in Fig. 3, thereby necessitating the use of models with more than two free parameters to accurately capture the atypical curve shape.

4.3. Spurious versions of Jovanović-I

In Sections 4.1 and 4.2, we conducted a thorough assessment of the Jovanović-I isotherm, examining its strengths and limitations as a modeling tool for representing water contaminant adsorption data. Our analysis provided valuable insights that are not commonly found in previous studies due to the use of flawed versions of the Jovanović-I model. Specifically, we identified two spurious forms of the Jovanović-I isotherm, with Eq. (23) being the first. This equation was initially used in the 2010s to describe the adsorption of dyes on activated carbons (Hadi et al., 2010, 2012; McKay et al., 2014).

$$\theta = \frac{q}{q_J} = [1 - \exp(bc)] \quad (23)$$

Upon comparing Eq. (23) with Eq. (5), it becomes apparent that the former is incorrect due to the absence of a negative sign in the argument of the exponential term. This error leads

to negative values of b when Eq. (23) is applied to experimental data, as demonstrated in Table 6, where several studies have used it to analyze water contaminant adsorption data. The parameter b in the Jovanović-I isotherm is considered an equilibrium constant with a positive value, similar to the parameter b_L in the Langmuir model, even though the theoretical foundation of the former is debated. Consequently, obtaining a negative value for b is nonsensical and contradicts the conventional definition of equilibrium constants. Surprisingly, certain studies have reported positive values of b from Eq. (23), as shown in Table 6. These positive values are erroneous because Eq. (23) predicts negative θ or q values when b is positive, as illustrated in Fig. 5. Consequently, it is impossible to obtain positive values of b by fitting Eq. (23) to hyperbolic isotherm data.

Table 6 Examples of water contaminant adsorption data modeled by Eq. (23).

Ref.	Water contaminant	Negative b (L mg ⁻¹)	Positive b (L mg ⁻¹)
Vargas et al. (2011)	Methylene blue	-1.9351	
Hossain et al. (2012)	Cu(II)	-1.237	
Wang et al. (2013)	Parachlorophenol	-0.0224; -0.0326; -0.0271; -0.0231; -0.0301	
Tümsek and Avcı (2013)	Acid Orange 95	-0.024; -0.1033; -0.0116	
Rangabhashiyam and Selvaraju (2015)	Cr(VI)	-0.0117; -0.0126; -0.0085	
Miraboutalebi et al. (2017)	Methylene blue	-0.007677	
Balci and Erkurt (2017)	Bisphenol-A	-0.0276	
Nayak and Pal (2020)	Acridine orange	-0.01; -0.015; -0.02	
Dolatabadi et al. (2022)	Chlorpyrifos	-0.85	
Kheradmand et al. (2023)	Rifampin	-0.1087	
Hadi et al. (2010)	Acid dyes		0.081; 0.492; 0.12; 0.114; 0.166
McKay et al. (2014)	Acid dyes		0.12; 0.114; 0.166
Mokhtari et al. (2016)	Methyl orange		3×10^{-6}
Wongcharee et al. (2019)	Methylene blue		0.0991; 0.2097; 0.3814
Balasubramani et al. (2020)	Metformin		0.24
Manjunatha et al. (2021)	Direct Blue 53; fluoride		0.1398; 0.03019
Rasoulzadeh et al. (2021)	Pd(II)		0.12
Jacob et al. (2022)	Chlorpyrifos		11.0614
Abutaleb et al. (2023)	Methylene blue		0.02698

Fig. 5. Plot of Eq. (23) with a positive b .

Eq. (24) corresponds to the second erroneous formulation of the Jovanović-I isotherm. This equation suggests that plotting $\ln(q)$ against c will yield a straight line. The linearized version of the Jovanović-I isotherm was initially used by Ghosh and Singh (2012) to describe herbicide adsorption on a soil-fly ash mixture. Subsequently, it has been used to analyze the adsorption data of different water contaminants, as shown in Table 7.

$$\ln(q) = \ln(q_J) - bc \quad (24)$$

Similar to the use of Eq. (23) for fitting adsorption data, using Eq. (24) for data correlation has resulted in both positive and negative values of b , as shown in Table 7. Since an increase in c leads to an increase in q , plotting $\ln(q)$ versus c should consistently yield a positively sloped straight line. According to Eq. (24), the positive slope should be equal to $-b$. As a result, a plot of $\ln(q)$ versus c should yield a negative numerical value for b . It appears that some previous studies reported a positive b due to simple arithmetic mistakes. However, as noted earlier, the equilibrium constant b is strictly positive in the Jovanović-I isotherm, and a negative value for b has no physical significance. This indicates a fundamental flaw in Eq. (24). Removing the logarithmic transformation from Eq. (24) results in Eq. (25) that partially resembles the original Jovanović-I isotherm described by Eq. (5). Fig. 6 illustrates a plot of Eq. (25) with a negative value of b . It is evident that Eq. (25) predicts a type III isotherm curve instead of a type I.

$$\theta = \frac{q}{q_J} = \exp(-bc) \quad (25)$$

Table 7 Examples of water contaminant adsorption data modeled by Eq. (24).

Ref.	Water contaminant	Negative b (L mg ⁻¹)	Positive b (L mg ⁻¹)
Kebir et al. (2015)	Cr(VI)	-0.0136; -0.0058; -0.0022; -0.0042; -0.0022; -0.0101	
Rangabhashiyam et al. (2016)	Cr(VI)	-0.005	
Ordenez et al. (2020)	Nitrate; phosphate	-3.7404; -842.3; -9.082; -35.94; -0.2435; -38.5	
Priyan et al. (2021)	Diclofenac	-0.0565	
Bandura et al. (2021)	Ibuprofen; bisphenol A; caffeine	-0.007; -0.006; -0.015	
Maity et al. (2021)	As(V); Cr(VI); Cd(II)	-0.061; -0.054; -0.238	
Maity et al. (2022)	As(V); Cd(II); Cr(VI)	-0.075; -0.101; -0.116	
Sivaraman et al. (2022)	Cr(VI)	-0.01; -0.0085	
Varadharajan et al. (2022)	Tetracycline	-0.06; -0.068	
Solisio et al. (2019)	Hg(II)		0.1067
Sahin et al. (2020)	Ibuprofen		0.047; 0.038; 0.025; 0.127; 0.082
Taneja et al. (2021)	Fluoride		0.62; 0.35
Jayakumar et al. (2021)	Cd(II)		0.0149
Pathy et al. (2022)	Malachite green		0.023; 0.02
Rahman and Raheem (2022)	Doxycycline		0.04; 0.05; 0.07
Salehi et al. (2023)	V(V)		0.1513

Fig. 6. Plot of Eq. (25) with a negative b .

The exact derivation of Eq. (24) remains unclear, but it is likely that it originated from an attempt to linearize the flawed Eq. (23), given that both equations have been presented together in some studies (Bandura et al., 2021; Maity et al., 2021, 2022; Pathy et al., 2022). However, since there is no obvious method to linearize Eq. (23), we believe that an incorrect approach was used. Here, we outline the probable steps involved in the derivation. Firstly, taking the logarithm of both sides of Eq. (23) results in Eq. (26). Next, an invalid logarithmic rule [$\ln(x - y) = \ln(x)/\ln(y) = \ln(x) - \ln(y)$] is applied to the right-hand side of Eq. (26), resulting in Eq. (27). By simplifying Eq. (27) using the fact that $\ln(1) = 0$, Eq. (28) is obtained. This equation is then rearranged to form Eq. (29). It is evident that Eq. (29) is formally equivalent

to Eq. (24). However, Eq. (29) is nonsensical since it is derived from the flawed Jovanović-I isotherm [Eq. (23)] using an illogical logarithmic rule.

$$\ln\left(\frac{q}{q_J}\right) = \ln[1 - \exp(bc)] \quad (26)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{q}{q_J}\right) = \ln(1) - bc \quad (27)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{q}{q_J}\right) = -bc \quad (28)$$

$$\ln(q) = \ln(q_J) - bc \quad (29)$$

While the use of the invalid logarithmic rule to linearize Eq. (23) is clearly improper, similar cases of inappropriate linearization have been observed in the field of water contaminant adsorption. For example, the Flory–Huggins and Halsey isotherms have also been subject to improper linearization, as highlighted in the work of Chu et al. (2023a, 2023b). It is worth pointing out that the flawed logarithmic rule, which misrepresents the quotient rule, is a common mistake made by students when working with logarithm properties (source: <https://logarithmicfunction.weebly.com/uploads/1/8/7/1/18718002/commonlogarithmerrors.pdf>).

Eqs. (23) and (24), despite their nonsensical nature, can be found in several review articles on isotherm models (Al-Ghouti and Da'ana, 2020; Kumar et al., 2023; Majd et al., 2022; Rangabhashiyam et al., 2014). The unquestioning acceptance of these patently erroneous equations by researchers and authors of these review articles is concerning and reflects poorly on the water contaminant adsorption community. It suggests that many members of this community may lack a fundamental understanding of isotherm models and a solid grasp of basic mathematical concepts.

4.4. Comparing BET, Jovanović-II, and new Jovanović-II variant

As discussed earlier, the Jovanović-II equation for multilayer adsorption [Eq. (6)] has not been commonly used to analyze sigmoid or type II isotherms in liquid phase adsorption. In this section, we will compare the effectiveness of the Jovanović-II equation, a modified version of it, and the BET equation (Brunauer et al., 1938) in fitting type II isotherm data. The BET equation for liquid phase adsorption is represented by Eq. (30), which includes three fitting parameters (q_s , b_f , and b_m) (Brião et al., 2022; Wang et al. 1998). In Eq. (30), b_f represents the equilibrium constant for the first layer adsorption (adsorbate-adsorbent interactions), while b_m denotes the equilibrium constant for multilayer adsorption (adsorbate-adsorbate interactions).

$$q = \left[\frac{q_s b_f c}{1 + (b_f - b_m) c} \right] \left[\frac{1}{1 - b_m c} \right] \quad (30)$$

In this study, we have introduced a modified version of the Jovanović-II equation, presented as Eq. (31), which incorporates four fitting parameters: q_J , b , k , and m . Given its resemblance to the power-law Jovanović-I equation, we have named it the power-law Jovanović-II equation. However, the exponent m in the power-law Jovanović-II equation does not have the same physical interpretation as the exponent n in the power-law Jovanović-I equation. In the latter model, n is defined as the heterogeneity parameter that affects the equilibrium constant b , which characterizes the interactions between adsorbate and adsorbent (Quiñones and Guiochon, 1996). On the contrary, in the power-law Jovanović-II equation, m is unrelated to the surface properties of the adsorbent. Instead, it modifies the equilibrium constant k , which describes adsorbate-adsorbate interactions in multilayer adsorption. Hence, m cannot be considered a heterogeneity parameter and is best treated as an empirical parameter.

$$q = q_J [1 - \exp(-bc)] \exp[(kc)^m] \quad (31)$$

Fig. 7 displays the fitting of a type II isotherm obtained from the study by Fiorentin et al. (2010) using the BET, Jovanović-II, and power-law Jovanović-II equations. The experimental isotherm describes the adsorption of reactive blue 5G dye on an orange bagasse biosorbent at 40 °C. Fig. 7 indicates that the performance of the Jovanović-II equation is comparable to that of the BET equation. Among the three models, the power-law Jovanović-II equation provides the most accurate fit. This observation is supported by the APE values for the three models, as presented in Table 8. The table also shows that the power-law Jovanović-II equation is supported by the AW metric, justifying the use of four fitting parameters to capture the curve shape of the dye isotherm. Based on this analysis, it can be concluded that the Jovanović-II equation exhibits limited effectiveness in modeling type II isotherm data and does not offer any significant advantages over the BET equation.

Fig. 7. Fitting reactive blue 5G adsorption data (Fiorentin et al., 2010) with the BET (A), Jovanović-II (B), and power-law Jovanović-II (C) equations.

Table 8 Parameter estimates and statistical metrics for the fits of the BET, Jovanović-II, and power-law Jovanović-II equations to reactive blue 5G adsorption data (Fiorentin et al., 2010).^a

Isotherm	Eq.	Parameter	Value (standard error)	Statistical metric	Value	Statistical metric	Value
BET	(30)	q_s	25.76 (1.9)	APE	10.4	AW	0.0
		b_f	0.345 (0.2)				
		b_m	0.006 (0.0003)				
Jovanović-II	(6)	q_J	20.44 (2.5)	APE	9.7	AW	0.0
		b	0.248 (0.19)				
		k	0.011 (0.001)				
Power-law Jovanović-II	(31)	q_J	37.68 (1.6)	APE	4.7	AW	100.0
		b	0.079 (0.01)				
		k	0.008 (0.0001)				
		m	4.165 (0.53)				

^a q_s and q_J are in mg g^{-1} ; b_f , b_m , b , and k are in L mg^{-1} ; m is dimensionless; APE and AW are in %.

4.5. Derivation of global isotherms

Surface heterogeneity plays a significant role in practical adsorption systems. In the theory of adsorption on energetically heterogeneous solid surfaces, it is assumed that the range of adsorption energies can be effectively represented by a continuous distribution function. The relationship between the measured (global) isotherm, the local isotherm, and the energy distribution function is described by the adsorption integral equation, which belongs to the class of Fredholm integral equations of the first kind. To obtain the global isotherm from the adsorption integral equation, a common approach involves using a local isotherm expressed in an explicit analytical form and assuming a particular functional form for the energy distribution.

The Jovanović-I model, along with various energy distribution functions, has been used in previous gas adsorption studies to derive global isotherms for heterogeneous adsorbents

(Hassan et al., 1992; Hines et al., 1990; Jaroniec and Piotrowska, 1986; Misra, 1973; Sircar, 1984). In this study, we will use the Jovanović-I, Jovanović-II, and power-law Jovanović-II equations as the local isotherms, in conjunction with the Sips distribution (Debord et al., 2016a, 2016b), to determine their respective global isotherms. All three Jovanović equations have been reformulated according to Eq. (32), with the local isotherm denoted as $\theta(b,c)$ and $A(c)$ defined as follows: for Jovanović-I, $A(c) = 1$; for Jovanović-II, $A(c) = \exp(kc)$; and for power-law Jovanović-II, $A(c) = \exp[(kc)^m]$.

$$\theta(b,c) = A(c)[1 - \exp(-bc)] \quad (32)$$

Eq. (33) defines the global isotherm $\Theta(c)$ for a heterogeneous adsorbent, where $f(b)$ is the probability density function (p.d.f.) for the random variable $b (\geq 0)$. By substituting Eq. (32) into Eq. (33), Eq. (34) can be obtained.

$$\Theta(c) = \int_0^{\infty} \theta(b,c) f(b) db \quad (33)$$

$$\Theta(c) = \int_0^{\infty} A(c)[1 - \exp(-bc)] f(b) db \quad (34)$$

As $A(c)$ is independent of b , rearranging Eq. (34) yields Eq. (35). The first integral in Eq. (35) denotes the total probability and has a value of 1 by definition. The second integral corresponds to the Laplace transform of $f(b)$. Consequently, Eq. (35) can be simplified to Eq. (36).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Theta(c)}{A(c)} &= \int_0^{\infty} [1 - \exp(-bc)] f(b) db \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} f(b) db - \int_0^{\infty} \exp(-bc) f(b) db \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{\Theta(c)}{A(c)} = 1 - \int_0^{\infty} \exp(-bc) f(b) db \quad (36)$$

For the Sips distribution (Debord et al., 2016a), Eq. (37) provides the p.d.f. for b , where α is a positive real exponent, ϕ^* is equal to the fractional part of α multiplied by π [$\phi^* = \pi \cdot \text{frac}(\alpha)$], and K_d represents the mean dissociation constant. With this p.d.f., we can solve the integral in Eq. (36). The resulting solution is presented in the study by Debord et al. (2016a) in the context of adsorption kinetics. It has been adapted to the equilibrium scenario and presented as Eq. (38) in this work, where E_α denotes the Mittag-Leffler function. The Mittag-Leffler function is defined in Eq. (39) as a series expansion with the gamma function (Γ) applied to a specific number.

$$f(b) = \frac{\alpha \sin(\phi^*)}{\phi^*} \cdot \frac{K_d^\alpha b^{\alpha-1}}{1 + 2(K_d b)^\alpha \cos(\phi^*) + (K_d b)^{2\alpha}} \quad (37)$$

$$\int_0^\infty \exp(-bc) f(b) db = E_\alpha \left[-\left(\frac{c}{K_d}\right)^\alpha \right] \quad (38)$$

$$E_\alpha(x) = 1 + \frac{x}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{x^2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} + \dots \quad (39)$$

When Eq. (38) is inserted into Eq. (36), we obtain Eq. (40), which represents the global isotherm. Although the Mittag-Leffler function has gained widespread use in kinetic studies (Mainardi, 2020), it has not previously been used as an adsorption isotherm. Therefore, we can refer to Eq. (40) as the Mittag-Leffler isotherm.

$$\Theta(c) = A(c) \left\{ 1 - E_\alpha \left[-\left(\frac{c}{K_d}\right)^\alpha \right] \right\} \quad (40)$$

Prior studies by Jaroniec and Piotrowska (1986) and Sircar (1984) have used a gamma distribution of binding constants. In these cases, the function $f(b)$ is given by Eq. (41), resulting in the global isotherm described by Eq. (42). Notably, when $A(c) = 1$ and $\alpha = 1$, this global isotherm simplifies to the well-known Langmuir isotherm.

$$f(b) = \frac{K_d^\alpha b^{\alpha-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \exp(-K_d b) \quad (41)$$

$$\Theta(c) = A(c) \left[1 - \left(\frac{K_d}{K_d + c}\right)^\alpha \right] \quad (42)$$

4.6. Avenues for further research

The different forms of the Jovanović model evaluated in this work can be extended to describe multi-solute adsorption. For instance, the extension of the Jovanović-I isotherm to competitive multi-solute adsorption is exemplified by Eq. (43) (Sircar, 1991, 2020). Eqs. (44) and (45) present the corresponding expressions for competitive bi-solute adsorption. In these equations, s represents the number of competing solutes, and subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the first and second solutes, respectively. It should be noted that Eq. (43) was initially proposed for mixed gas adsorption (Sircar, 1991). A similar extension of the power-law Jovanović-I isotherm for the case of competitive bi-solute adsorption is described in Eqs. (46) and (47) (Quiñones and Guiochon, 1998). Currently, we are investigating the applicability of Eqs. (44)–(47) for the analysis of bi-solute adsorption data and the findings will be reported in future publications.

$$\theta_i = \frac{b_i c_i}{\sum_{i=1}^s b_i c_i} \left[1 - \exp \left(- \sum_{i=1}^s b_i c_i \right) \right] \quad (43)$$

$$\theta_1 = \frac{b_1 c_1}{b_1 c_1 + b_2 c_2} \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[- (b_1 c_1 + b_2 c_2) \right] \right\} \quad (44)$$

$$\theta_2 = \frac{b_2 c_2}{b_1 c_1 + b_2 c_2} \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[- (b_1 c_1 + b_2 c_2) \right] \right\} \quad (45)$$

$$\theta_1 = \frac{b_1 c_1}{b_1 c_1 + b_2 c_2} \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[- (b_1 c_1 + b_2 c_2)^n \right] \right\} \quad (46)$$

$$\theta_2 = \frac{b_2 c_2}{b_1 c_1 + b_2 c_2} \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[- (b_1 c_1 + b_2 c_2)^n \right] \right\} \quad (47)$$

The Jovanović-II isotherm has also been extended to describe mixed gas adsorption (Jaroneic, 1976b). However, both the original Jovanović-II isotherm and its newly proposed power law version have limited practical relevance in the context of multi-solute adsorption in liquid-solid systems. This is due to the scarcity of competitive type II isotherm data.

Additionally, we are actively investigating the use of the global isotherms defined by Eqs. (40) and (42) for determining the isosteric enthalpy of adsorption. This can be achieved through either the Clausius–Clapeyron approach or virial analysis (Nuhnen and Janiak, 2020). The enthalpy of adsorption plays a significant role in understanding adsorption processes and provides valuable insights into the interactions between adsorbate and adsorbent. Furthermore, analyzing the enthalpy of adsorption in relation to the adsorbed amount enables a comprehensive understanding of the energetic heterogeneity of a solid surface. This specific area of study holds practical significance and currently constitutes the central focus of our ongoing research efforts.

5. Conclusions

The key results of this work are the following:

- Two commonly used, flawed versions of the Jovanović-I isotherm can produce negative adsorption equilibrium constants when applied to isotherm data. Such results are nonsensical because they violate the standard definition of equilibrium constants.
- The authentic Jovanović-I isotherm and the Langmuir isotherm exhibit distinct fits of favorable isotherm data. Typically, the Jovanović-I isotherm attains saturation at lower liquid phase concentrations compared to the Langmuir isotherm.

- Although both isotherms can satisfactorily fit favorable isotherm data with reasonable accuracy, their effectiveness diminishes when it comes to describing highly favorable or rectangular isotherm data, as well as data that lacks a distinct plateau and shows a gradual increase in q at higher concentrations.
- The Jovanović-II isotherm for multilayer adsorption, which is rarely used, exhibits only mediocre performance when describing sigmoid or type II isotherm data and does not provide any significant advantages over the BET equation. However, a modified version of the Jovanović-II isotherm, namely the power-law Jovanović-II, introduced in this study is substantially superior to the original formulation.
- By using the Jovanović-I, Jovanović-II, and power-law Jovanović-II equations as local isotherms, it is possible to develop global isotherms for modeling adsorption on heterogeneous adsorbents.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at

Nomenclature

$A(c)$	Parameter defined in Eq. (32) [-]
b	Jovanović equilibrium constant for monolayer adsorption [L mg^{-1} or Pa^{-1}]
b°	Standard Jovanović equilibrium constant [-]
b_1	Jovanović equilibrium constant for the first solute in a bi-solute system [L mg^{-1}]
b_2	Jovanović equilibrium constant for the second solute in a bi-solute system [L mg^{-1}]
b_A	Jovanović equilibrium constant for type A site [L mg^{-1}]
b_B	Jovanović equilibrium constant for type B site [L mg^{-1}]
b_f	BET equilibrium constant for the first layer adsorption [L mg^{-1}]
b_L	Langmuir equilibrium constant [L mg^{-1} or Pa^{-1}]

b_L°	Standard Langmuir equilibrium constant [-]
b_m	BET equilibrium constant for multilayer adsorption [L mg ⁻¹]
c	Equilibrium liquid phase concentration [mg L ⁻¹]
c°	Standard liquid phase concentration [1 mol L ⁻¹]
E_α	Mittag-Leffler function [-]
$f(b)$	Probability density function [mg L ⁻¹]
h	Number of fitting parameters [-]
k	Jovanović equilibrium constant for multilayer adsorption [L mg ⁻¹ or Pa ⁻¹]
K°	Thermodynamic adsorption equilibrium constant [-]
K_0	Partitioning equilibrium constant [L mg ⁻¹]
$K_{0,J}$	Jovanović partitioning equilibrium constant [L mg ⁻¹]
$K_{0,L}$	Langmuir partitioning equilibrium constant [L mg ⁻¹]
K_d	Mean dissociation constant [mg L ⁻¹]
m	Empirical parameter [-]
n	Heterogeneity parameter [-]
p	Equilibrium gas pressure [Pa]
q	Equilibrium adsorbed phase concentration [mg g ⁻¹]
q_{cal}	Value of q calculated from a model [mg g ⁻¹]
q_{exp}	Experimental value of q [mg g ⁻¹]
q_J	Jovanović saturation capacity [mg g ⁻¹]
q_{JA}	Jovanović saturation capacity for type A site [mg g ⁻¹]
q_{JB}	Jovanović saturation capacity for type B site [mg g ⁻¹]
q_s	Langmuir saturation capacity [mg g ⁻¹]
R	Universal gas constant [kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
s	Number of competing solutes [-]
t	Dimensionless parameter (c/K_d) [-]
T	Absolute temperature [K]
T_0	Reference temperature [K]
w	Number of competing models [-]
z	Number of data points [-]
<i>Greek letters</i>	
α	Positive real exponent [-]
ϕ^*	Fractional part of α multiplied by π [-]
λ	Generic equilibrium constant in Eq. (4) [Pa ⁻¹]

θ	Surface coverage [-]
σ	Exponent in Eq. (4) [-]
ΔC_p°	Difference in heat capacities between the adsorbate-adsorbent complex and the unbound adsorbate and unoccupied binding sites [kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
ΔG°	Standard Gibbs energy [kJ mol ⁻¹]
ΔH°	Standard enthalpy of adsorption [kJ mol ⁻¹]
ΔH°_T	ΔH° evaluated at T [kJ mol ⁻¹]
$\Delta H^\circ_{T_0}$	ΔH° evaluated at T_0 [kJ mol ⁻¹]
ΔS°	Standard entropy of adsorption [kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
ΔS°_T	ΔS° evaluated at T [kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
$\Delta S^\circ_{T_0}$	ΔS° evaluated at T_0 [kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
Δ_i	AIC value calculated from Eq. (10) [-]
Γ	Gamma function [-]
$\Theta(c)$	Global isotherm for a heterogeneous adsorbent [-]

Abbreviations

AIC	Corrected Akaike Information Criterion
AIC _{<i>i</i>}	AIC value for the <i>i</i> -th model
AIC _{<i>s</i>}	AIC value for the model with the lowest score
APE	Average percent error
AW	Akaike weight
SSR	Sum of squared residuals

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